

A Web Application for Direct Market Access for Farmers
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Abstract

The “Web Application for Direct Market Access for Farmers” is developed to help farmers sell agricultural products directly to customers through an online platform. The system allows farmers to upload product details and users to view and purchase products easily. It includes separate modules for admin, farmers, and users to manage products and orders efficiently. Developed using PHP and MySQL, the application reduces manual work, saves time, and improves direct marketing opportunities for farmers.

1. Introduction

Agriculture plays an important role in everyday life and the economy. Many farmers face difficulties in selling products directly to customers because they depend on local markets and intermediaries. The “Web Application for Direct Market Access for Farmers” is developed to provide an online platform where farmers can sell agricultural products directly to users. The system helps farmers manage product details, improve market access, and reduce manual work through a simple and user-friendly web application.

2. Objectives

- To provide direct online market access for farmers
- To reduce the dependency on intermediaries
- To simplify agricultural product selling
- To help customers purchase products easily
- To maintain records digitally
- To reduce manual work and time consumption

3. Existing System

In the current method, farmers mainly depend on local markets and agents to sell their products. This process requires more effort and time. Farmers must travel to markets frequently and may not receive proper profit for their products.

Limitations of Existing System

More manual work

Time-consuming process

Difficult product management

Lack of direct customer interaction

Reduced profit for farmers

4. Proposed System

The proposed system provides a web-based platform where farmers can directly sell their products to customers. Farmers can register, upload products, and manage their details through the application.

Customers can search products, check prices, and place orders online. The admin controls the entire system and manages users, farmers, products, and order details.

Advantages of Proposed System

Easy product management

Faster communication

Reduced manual activities

Better market opportunities for farmers

Easy access to product information

Online order management

5. Modules Description

Admin Module

The admin manages the complete system. The admin can view and maintain farmer details, user information, products, and orders.

Farmer Module

Farmers can register into the system and upload agricultural products with details such as price, quantity, and description. Farmers can also update product details.

User Module

Users can register and log in to the application. They can view products, place orders, and check product information.

6. System Requirements

Hardware Requirements

Processor: Intel i3 or higher

RAM: 4GB

Hard Disk: 500GB

Software Requirements

Operating System: Windows 10

Front End: HTML, CSS, JavaScript

Back End: PHP

Database: MySQL

7. Technologies Used

HTML

CSS

JavaScript

PHP

MySQL

8. Testing

The system is tested using different testing methods to ensure proper functionality.

Types of Testing

Unit Testing

Integration Testing

Validation Testing

Black Box Testing

White Box Testing

9. Conclusion

The “Web Application for Direct Market Access for Farmers” provides an efficient solution for online agricultural product selling. The system helps farmers connect directly with customers and reduces the difficulties faced in traditional selling methods.

The application improves product accessibility, reduces manual work, and provides a simple platform for managing agricultural sales and orders.

10. Future Enhancement

Online payment integration

Mobile application development

Delivery tracking system

Product recommendation system

Multi-language support

11. References

Books

Roger Pressman – Software Engineering

PHP and MySQL Web Development

Websites

W3Schools

PHP Official Site

MySQL Official Site